

Supplementary Material for: Architectural Relationship between Neural Cellular Automata and ConvLSTM

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Testing State Value Clipping

An experiment was conducted to evaluate the necessity of clipping state variables across the models. While ConvLSTM utilizes a tanh function to explicitly bound the value range of its hidden state \mathcal{H} , the other models (ConvLSTM+1, ConvLSTM+1+2, and NCA) do not explicitly restrict the domain of their state variables. Here, the impact of imposing such restrictions on model training was investigated.

To minimize the influence of external disturbances and isolate the pure effect on learning dynamics, the training behaviors of the models on the Fixed-step Pattern Growth task, both with and without state clipping, were compared. Models were trained for 5,000 iterations with a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} across 5 random seeds, following the main text for other configurations. State values were clipped to the range $[-10, 10]$. Although ConvLSTM naturally bounds its hidden state \mathcal{H} within $[-1, 1]$, its cell state \mathcal{C} can encompass a broader range. Since rigidly restricting the state variables of the other models to $[-1, 1]$ could excessively compromise their representational capacity, a wider clipping threshold of $[-10, 10]$ was chosen.

The learning curves for the clipped and unclipped variants of these three models are presented in Figure S1. Notably, for the unclipped ConvLSTM+1+2 model, training diverged in one of the five runs; hence, the plot displays the results from the four successful seeds. The results indicate that clipping noticeably improves the training stability of ConvLSTM+1+2. Conversely, ConvLSTM+1 exhibits no such improvement in stability with clipping. For the standard NCA model, the learning curves with and without clipping are nearly identical, demonstrating highly stable training in both scenarios.

The lack of improvement in ConvLSTM+1’s stability can likely be attributed to its inherent update bounds. Although the state \mathcal{S} in ConvLSTM+1 lacks an explicit range limit, the update increments added at each step are inherently bounded by the tanh activation, which mitigates drastic state fluctuations. In contrast, ConvLSTM+1+2 extends this update rule to an MLP and lacks any such value bounding, rendering it

more susceptible to training instability.

Interestingly, the standard NCA model achieves remarkable training stability without any clipping, despite similarly lacking explicit mechanisms to bound its state values or update increments. We hypothesize that this stability stems from the smooth optimization landscape provided by residual learning (He et al., 2016), a phenomenon thoroughly explored and documented in the broader deep learning literature (Li et al., 2018).

Visualization of Generated Patterns

Figure S2 visually compares the models across four target emojis under the Regeneration setting. The generated patterns illustrate the steady state of each model, obtained by allowing the system to grow from a single seed state for 200 update steps. Since the models were evaluated across five different random seeds for each experimental setup, the images presented in Figure S2 specifically display the results from the best-performing seed, defined as the run that achieved the lowest Mean Squared Error (MSE) at step 200.

Consistent with the quantitative results discussed in the main text, the visualizations demonstrate that models utilizing an MLP for their update rules (i.e., ConvLSTM+1+2 and NCA) successfully achieve high-fidelity pattern reproduction. In contrast, the standard ConvLSTM and ConvLSTM+1 models struggle to capture fine spatial details, often resulting in blurred images or noisy, coarse textures.

Furthermore, a direct visual comparison between ConvLSTM+1+2 and NCA reveals nearly indistinguishable high-fidelity results for most targets. This visual parity reinforces the conclusion that the MLP-based update rule is the primary driver for achieving high spatial resolution. However, a noticeable difference emerges in the Tropical Fish target, where NCA produces a visibly sharper pattern. This discrepancy likely highlights the inherent training instability of ConvLSTM+1+2 caused by its dynamic gating mechanism. In contrast, the fixed-gate, residual structure of NCA provides a smoother optimization landscape, ensuring stable and consistent convergence regardless of the target pattern.

Figure S1: Learning curves for each model with and without state variable clipping. Models were trained across five random seeds, with loss progression displayed on a logarithmic scale. Solid lines represent the mean loss, while shaded regions indicate the standard deviation (calculated in the log space). For visual clarity, the plotted curves are smoothed using a moving average with a window size of 10. Note that for the unclipped ConvLSTM+1+2 model, training diverged in one of the five runs; therefore, its plot displays the mean and standard deviation from the four successful seeds.

Figure S2: Visualization of steady-state pattern reproduction. Models were trained under the Regeneration setting and grown from a single seed for 200 update steps. For each model and target, the image from the best-performing seed (lowest MSE at step 200 out of five trials) is shown.

References

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